

FoodSafety4EU

MULTI-STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM
FOR FOOD SAFETY IN EUROPE

*Net Mapping to analyse the System-Policy-Society
collaboration system in risk analysis*

Guideline to conduct an on-line Net-Map Analysis workshop

Pieterneel Luning
Niels van der Linden

Wageningen University & Research

 FoodSafety4EU has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101000613

<https://foodsafetyplatform.eu>

1. Introduction	3
1.1 What is Net Map?	3
1.2 How will we use Net Map in the FS4EU project?	3
2. Guidelines to prepare for the online Net Map workshop	7
2.1 Who to involve in organising the online Net Map workshop?	7
2.2 What will be the food safety issue for which the Net Map will be done?	7
2.3 How to acquire participants for the workshop?	8
2.4 What to brief to the participants before the workshop?	8
2.5 How to get access to the Miro board?	9
2.6 How to make break out rooms and set a limit for conducting a task?	9
3. Guidelines for conducting the NetMap workshop in MIRO	10
3.1 Introduction to the workshop	11
3.2 Explanation of Net Map methodology and Miro tools	11
3.3 Getting to know each other	12
3.4 Identifying the stakeholders and their goals- stakeholder mapping	12
3.5 Identifying and characterising stakeholder links- social network	13
3.6 Assessing stakeholders' influence on risk analysis process- power mapping	15
3.7 Identifying and prioritising constraints in the SPS collaboration system	15
3.8 Finalising the workshop	16

1. Introduction

This document consists of guidelines for the HUB leaders to prepare and conduct the online Net Map workshop. For the online workshop, we adjusted the Net Map methodology and use *Miro and Mentimeter as digital tools*. First, we provide some information on what a Net Map is and how we will use it in the FS4EU project. Section 2 describes how to prepare the workshop (technical issues, finding participants, etc.). Section 3 describes how to conduct the online Net Mapping (e.g. instructions for the facilitator, the tasks for participants, roles, planning).

1.1 What is Net Map?

Net Map is an interview-based mapping tool that can be used by researchers, facilitators, and implementers to (1) visualize implicit knowledge and understand the interplay of complex formal and informal networks, power relations, and actors' goals; (2) uncover sources of conflicts as well as potentials for cooperation; (3) facilitate knowledge exchange and learning processes; and (4) develop visions and strategies to achieve common goals (Schiffer & Hauck, 2010).

Picture of a NetMap made in a live setting showing actors (pions), their goals (the codes on the sticky notes), their links (the arrows) and their power/influence (number of rings) in the network.

1.2 How will we use Net Map in the FS4EU project?

Overall, the Net Map methodology can be used to analyse and characterise social networks that have a shared goal. The stakeholders in the SPS system in risk analysis have as a shared goal to adequately characterise, manage and communicate (emerging) food safety risks.

The Net Map methodology has been adjusted to make it suitable for achieving our WP3 goals and for conducting the online workshop. The overall goals of task 3.2 in WP3 are to identify who are the stakeholders in the society-policy-science (SPS) collaboration system, and what are their needs for improvement in their relations, resources and capabilities in conducting risk analysis (i.e. risk assessment, risk communication, risk management) of a specific (emerging) food safety issue.

For the online NetMap analysis, we use a predefined food safety issue for a specific country/region. Figure 1 shows the steps of the Net Map analysis. Below you can find a more detailed description of the steps.

Figure 1- Steps in the NetMap analysis

Step 1 contains the so-called **stakeholder mapping**. Stakeholders in the SPS collaboration system in risk analysis are any legal persons (organisation or individual, e.g. companies or people) that can have any influence on the risk analysis process (i.e. risk assessment, management and/or communication). Table 1 shows examples of stakeholders in the risk analysis process (described in general terms) belonging to science, policy, or society.

For the online Net Map analysis, participants will specify the stakeholders (name of entity/organisation), put the abbreviation on the MAP. The full details and the classification into the society, policy or science category will be reported in a Table (see section 3).

Table 1 Examples of typical stakeholders in the risk analysis process classified into science-policy-society (SPS-system)

Stakeholder (general description)	Category (S-P-S)
(Agricultural) University	Science
Research Institute	Science
Reference lab	Science
Food Safety Authority	Policy
Ministry of Health	Policy
Certification body	Policy
Consumer organisation	Society
(Agricultural) Cooperative	Society
Supermarket chain	Society

Step 2 aims at gaining insight into the **goals of the stakeholders** within the risk analysis process.

For the online Net Map analysis, there are three goals including risk assessment, management, and communication. Per the overall goal, we defined subgoals based on previous expert discussions. Participants will describe per actor these specific subgoals and report this in a Table (see section 3).

Table 2- The three goals (risk assessment, management, and communication) with typical subgoals (primary goals or responsibilities of an actor in the network; coded as RA1..., RM 1...and RC 1...) and a brief explanation.

Overall goals*	Subgoals	Short explanation
Risk assessment	RA1: risk identification	Assessing hazards and exposure pathways
	RA2: data collection	Collecting data on consumption etc. for risk assessment
	RA3: risk assessment	Performing the risk assessment
	Others	
Risk management	RM1: policy development	Development of policy
	RM2: setting/proposing legislation	Proposing and/or setting legislation (solicited or unsolicited)
	RM3: enforcement	Executing inspections, monitoring
	Others	
Risk communication	RC1: developing risk communication	Development of risk communication
	RC2: dissemination of risk communication	Dissemination of risk communication to society
	RC3: evaluating impact/efficiency	Evaluation of impact and efficiency of risk communication
	Others:	

*Depending on the overall goal of the stakeholder, it obtains a differently shaped sticky note to show immediately the different goals of the stakeholders on the Net Map.

Step 3 contains the so-called **(social) network mapping** showing how the actors are linked. This step gives insight into the character of relations between the identified stakeholders.

For the online NetMap analysis, we defined four types of relations as shown in Table 3.

The character of linkage*	Explanation
Regulatory responsibility	Legally established relations e.g. FSAs as assigned monitoring regulatory body, companies submitting food safety issues
Information sharing	Consultation or providing data/information, not legally established, e.g. 3 rd party data collection for risk assessment, companies sharing data with industry organisation
Communication from/to society	Consumers reporting issues to FSA, companies communicating on safe practices
Others	

*Each linkage is shown in the NetMap as a coloured arrow with a certain direction (-->). Between stakeholders, you can have a one-sided, two-sided or no link. In this way, the social network is created showing the links (and characters of these links) between the stakeholders.

Step 4 contains the so-called **power mapping**. This step gives insight into the influence of each actor in the SPS collaboration system on the overall risk analysis process. Some stakeholders have more influence on the process and outcome than others. To implement interventions, it is useful to have insight into the relative influence of the various stakeholders on the risk analysis process and outcome.

For the online Net Map analysis, we will use Mentimeter (a digital tool for voting) to allow individual participants to give anonymously ‘power’ scores to each stakeholder.

After these four steps, we have a Net Map with stakeholders (their name (as abbreviation) and goal) connected through coloured arrows (showing the linkages and type of relation) and the size of each actor (small, medium large sticky note) indicates their power/influence on the risk analysis process and outcome. This map will serve as a basis for **identifying and characterising major constraints** in the SPS collaboration system in risk analysis. Table 3 shows the different categories of constraints and a short explanation.

Table 3- Explanation of the different categories of constraints

Category of constraint	Explanation
Capabilities	Refers to lack of mandate to make decisions Refers to lack of knowledge, expertise
Resources	Refers to insufficient finances, manpower, equipment, time (etc.)
Relations	Refers to the absence of contacts (links), relations that do not function properly
Others	

2. Guidelines to prepare for the online Net Map workshop

This section gives some guidance on how to prepare the online Net Map workshop. The section is organised around frequently asked questions.

2.1 Who to involve in organising the online Net Map workshop?

To organise the online Net Map workshop, we advise you to have a facilitator (also called moderator), a (research) assistant with expertise in the fields of risk analysis, a technical assistant, and two students (with knowledge of risk analysis and preferably English skills) who can make notes of the additional information obtained during tasks. Each has another role and different tasks as briefly described in Table 4.

Table 4 Overview of roles and tasks

The facilitator* guides the participants through the Net Map process by
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) Introducing the programme2) Explaining the tasks3) Maintaining the focus on the tasks/goals to achieve (e.g. by visiting break out rooms)4) Guiding the presentations of task outcomes and monitoring the time5) Guiding plenary discussions
The research assistant helps the facilitator content-wise
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) Sending the Miro link in advance together with background information about the workshop program2) Monitoring the Miro frames during conducting of the tasks by the groups3) Answering content-wise questions4) Giving tips on organising the Maps (e.g. clustering of actors according to science, policy, and society) during visits to the breakout rooms5) Synthesising the Maps from the groups into one map (if necessary)6) Keeping track of the chat for content-wise issues/questions
The technical assistant supports by
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) checking the Miro link2) organising in advance the breakout rooms3) installing a clock to monitor the task duration4) keeping track of the chat for technical issues5) solving technical issues
The (2) students support by
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) making notes of additional information mentioned by participants during the tasks2) fill in the Tables with the additional information necessary for data analysis

*Please be aware that the facilitator should not contribute to the Net Map analysis content-wise. For information about the typical skills of a facilitator, see the FSO lab manual.

2.2 What will be the food safety issue for which the Net Map will be done?

The food safety issue will be defined based on the information obtained through the in-depth interviews with FSA conducted by Celine (UGent) and Niels (WUR). There are some options

- a) All HUBS have a different food safety issue specific to one country (for which the participants will be recruited). This scenario will result in a broad variety of constraints identified through four different Net Maps.

- b) Two food safety issues will be defined (based on the in-depth interviews) and each will be elaborated on in two workshops for a specific country. This scenario allows for the comparison of constraints identified through the NetMap workshops in two countries per food safety issue.
- c) One food safety issue will be selected for all HUBS. This scenario will provide insight into constraints for the same food safety issue but in four different countries, each with a unique SPS collaboration system.

The first scenario hampers comparison and the last scenario is challenging as there is likely no food safety issue equally relevant for all HUBS. The most likely scenario is 2. In the NetMap pilot session with the HUB leaders, a final decision will be made.

2.3 How to acquire participants for the workshop?

The idea is that you acquire 10-12 participants that have insight into the stakeholder SPS collaboration system in risk analysis, with specific attention to the selected food safety issue (can be microbiological or chemical) for a specific country. Participants can be actual stakeholders in science, policy or society contributing to risk analysis or have broad expertise in risk analysis of (emerging) food safety issues.

You can use a kind of snowball approach, which means that you start with a crucial (well-known) stakeholder in the SPS collaboration system (e.g. somebody working at a Food Safety Authority organisation) and ask for other contacts that represent a stakeholder or has the right expertise related to the FS issue. Please check the list of FS4EU supporting partners as well. The group must consist of a variety of stakeholders/experts to obtain accurate Net Maps.

2.4 What to brief to the participants before the workshop?

Note: The **invitation for the workshop** with the day and starting time-ending (invitation via Zoom or MS Teams) needs to be sent as soon as possible to ensure that people will be available. You can use a poll to check for availability or set a date (far in advance).

After acquiring the participants, the facilitator/research assistant sends an email (2 weeks in advance) containing the following information:

1. Express your appreciation for the confirmed participation on behalf of FS4EU
2. An overview of the Net Map workshop programme (including the schedule)
3. Kindly ask the participants to check the attachment with background information so they can already think about possible input
4. Link to the Miro board
5. Information about Mentimeter
6. In attachment 1 - the letter of consent
7. In attachment 2 - background information about Net Mapping, with the list of possible stakeholders, information about the goals, links, and type of constraints (HUB leaders can use the text from section 1- Introduction).

2.5 How to get access to the Miro board?

Link: https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_lwl3LZg=/

The HUB leaders will get a link to their MIRO board for their workshop. The Miro board is designed by WUR (Niels/Pieterneel) and the link will be sent by provided by Niels to Celine (coordinates the communication to the other HUB leaders).

For the actual Net Map workshop, the team (technical assistant, research assistant, facilitator) must check the link in advance and practice with the Miro board. The link must be sent to the participants via email (briefing). Moreover, we advise you to put the link in the chat (of Zoom or MS Teams).

Note: currently, FS4EU is arranging a Miro license which has broad applications. In the pilot NetMap on the 13th of October 2021, the HUB leaders will practice with the Miro Board.

2.6 How to make break out rooms and set a limit for conducting a task?

Break out rooms need to be prepared preferably in advance to enable group work. Once the participants confirmed their participation, you can make groups (we advise two groups of 5-6 participants). Take care that each group consists of different stakeholders/experts.

When participants enter the ZOOM or MS Teams platform, they should fill in their names to enable communication between participants. Please do not forget to ‘name’ the breakout rooms (e.g. groups 1 and 2) and use these names for the Miro frames where they must conduct their tasks.

In the Net Mapping, participants conduct mostly group tasks, for these tasks they get a certain amount of time to work in the breakout rooms. In the breakout rooms, you can set a time limit for each breakout session. For some instructions in Zoom and MS teams see the following links:

- [Using breakout rooms in MS Teams](#)
- [Using breakout rooms in Zoom](#)

3. Guidelines for conducting the NetMap workshop in MIRO

This section describes the activities of the Net Map workshop program including the instructions for the facilitator (and research/technical assistant if necessary); the description of the tasks and how to organise them (as a group via a break out rooms or individually); instructions to participants (rapporteur, making notes with additional information). All **information is connected to the specific Miro frames** that together shape the Miro board. slides)

Overview with an indication of time per item (breaks not shown)

- 3.1 Introduction to the workshop – [5 minutes]
 - Welcome and workshop program
 - Introduction to FS4EU research work package 3
- 3.2 Explanation Net Map methodology and Miro tools [5 minutes]
 - Steps in Net Map methodology
 - Demonstration of using Miro tools (sticky notes, arrows, etc.)
- 3.3 Getting to know each other [10 minutes]
- 3.4 Identifying stakeholders and their goals [35 minutes]
 - BREAK -
- 3.5 Identifying and characterising relations between stakeholders [40 minutes]
 - BREAK -
- 3.6 Assessing the stakeholders' power/influence in the SPS collaboration system in risk analysis 20 minutes]
- 3.7 Identifying and prioritising constraints in the SPS collaboration system and suggesting recommendations [35 minutes]
- 3.8 Wrapping up [5 minutes]

3.1 Introduction to the workshop

The **goals** are to introduce the workshop program, the research objective and food safety issue

The facilitator welcomes the participants and shows the topics of the overall programme

Miro frame 1- showing an overall program of the workshop (see items below):

- Introduction to the research
- Steps in the Net Map analysis methodology
- Basics of the digital tools (MIRO/Mentimeter)
- Getting to know each other
- Conducting the Net Mapping

The facilitator says a few words about the FS4EU project, explains the objective of WP3 task 3.2 and what is expected from the participants. After this, the facilitator activates one of the two movies explaining the food safety issue for which the NetMap analysis will be conducted.

Miro frame 2- showing the points for the research introduction (see items below, in grey some details)

- Introduction to FS4EU
(only explain the overall aim, mention the main WP's and WP3 in particular: Title: Improvement of roadmaps for the future FSS - integration and forecasting. Please also check the project description)
- Aim of WP3 task 3.2
(To analyse the stakeholders in the SPS collaboration system in risk analysis to identify improvements in resources, capabilities, relations. Please explain the term SPS society-policy-science collaboration system. To analyse the SPS collaboration system we use the Net Map methodology which will be explained in the next frame)
- What is expected from participants?
- Explanation of the food safety issue for which the NetMap will be conducted
(the idea is that Niels will make for each FS a brief movie to introduce the issue → will be aiming to be done before 22/10/21)

Miro-frame 3 – with links to the two movies to inform about the selected food safety issue for which the NetMap analysis will be conducted.

3.2 Explanation of Net Map methodology and Miro tools

The **goals** are to get an insight into the steps in the Net Map methodology and familiarise themselves with the MIRO tools that will be used in the different tasks.

The facilitator briefly explains the steps in the NetMap methodology and clarifies the following concepts: SPS collaboration system, stakeholder, and risk analysis (explain that we include all aspects of assessment, management, and communication).

Miro frame 4 showing the steps of the Net Map analysis (note that the information about the NetMap steps and some definitions has been sent by email in an attachment).

The facilitator demonstrates how to use the various Miro tools that participants will apply in conducting the NetMap.

Miro frame 5 - to explain the use of Miro tools

- Interface layout (options left, right up and down)
- Use of post-its/different colours
- How to add text/figures/arrows

3.3 Getting to know each other

The **goal** is to inform participants about each other's work/expertise

The facilitator introduces task 1 and monitors the time

Miro frame 6 to get to know each other – Each Hub leader must add the map of their country/region for which the NetMap will be done

Task 1- The individual participants are asked to indicate the location of their organisation and briefly tell something about his/her background/expertise and current job (1 minute per person).

3.4 Identifying the stakeholders and their goals- stakeholder mapping

The overall **goal is** to create the stakeholder mapping including their goals in the risk-analysis process.

The facilitator explains that the first two steps of the NetMap analysis are combined into one task and then explains in detail task 2 (so what is expected from the participants and show the Miro board and Table A). The facilitator also mentions that the participants will be allocated to a breakout room (there will be two groups, and the technical assistant needs to take care of the automatic assignment to the groups). The facilitator explains that in each group, they must assign a rapporteur who will present the findings of the task. Furthermore, it will be explained that in each group, there will be an external note-taker (student role) who make notes of the additional information required in each task in Table A. There will be a clock and/or they will be informed when they have their last 5 minutes to accomplish their task.

Miro frame 7 - (group 1 and group 2) each group gets a frame where they must add the name of the stakeholders (as an abbreviation) on a differently shaped sticky note. There are three shapes, each represents another goal (risk assessment, management, or communication). They need to provide the details about the organisation and the subgoals (specific activities) in Table A.

Task 2- They are asked to establish **which stakeholders** (i.e. all legal persons in the SPS collaboration system, see section 1) are involved in the risk analysis process typical for the defined food safety issue. They use the list of pre-identified stakeholders (generally described) as a source of inspiration. They also need to consider to which category the stakeholder belongs: **society, policy or science and try to group the stakeholders accordingly.**

Next, they need to discuss for each stakeholder what is **their main goal** (i.e. assessment, management, or communication) and discuss and report their specific subgoal(s). These subgoals need to be reported in Table A. Below Table A, the various subgoals are defined as input for the detailed description (Hub leaders can find them in section 1).

They must put the **abbreviation of the stakeholder on a different shaped sticky note.** There are three shapes, for respectively risk assessment, management, and communication. In Table A, they must report the details about the typical activities they conduct (sub-goals).

If one stakeholder has e.g. two different departments, each responsible for a distinct overall goal (i.e. assessment and management), then they use two different shaped sticky notes (show abbreviations of the department) and report the details in Table A.

When time is over to complete the task time, the facilitator explains how the presentation will be done and how much time each group has for presenting. Furthermore, the facilitator guides the discussion and monitors the time.

Presentation of task 2 – participants in group 1 are asked to show their Miro frame and briefly explain their main outcomes (actors and goals). Participants in group 2 are asked to check during this presentation their main differences/other outcomes. In their presentation, they can focus on additional actors and other goals. These can be briefly discussed plenary.

- Break –

During the break, the research assistant makes a copy of the Miro frame of group 1 (when group 1 starts) and adds (together with the facilitator) the additional actors/goals as presented by group 2. They can also re-organise a bit the spreading of the actors on the Map. The synthesised Miro frame will serve as input for the next task.

3.5 Identifying and characterising stakeholder links- social network

The **goal** of this step in the NetMap methodology is to create the so-called social network. This network shows the links between the stakeholders and provides insight into the kind of relationship(s) that exist between them (if any).

After the break, the facilitator starts the session and asks to look first at the synthesised MAP and ask for any comments and if participants agree with the overall stakeholder Map.

Then, the facilitator introduces the concept of 'links' and the character of the links (i.e. relations). He/she explains the different categories of links and which coloured arrow belongs to each. The facilitator explains task 3 and that the participants will work in the same group (break out rooms). Furthermore, they need to assign another rapporteur and they will be supported by the same note keeper.

Miro frames 8 – (groups 1 and 2) show the synthesised Map of stakeholders and goals (i.e. the output of task 2). Each group has its MAP and the Miro frame contains differently coloured arrows that typify the various relationships/linkages. These arrows must be used to show identified linkages.

Task 3- The participants are asked to identify and characterise (by using the coloured arrows) the links (relations) between the stakeholders. There can be a one-sided or two-sided linkage/relation; so, one or two arrows can be used (or none) and each arrow can have a different character (another colour). The different types of categories are listed as codes on the Miro frame, but the participants are asked to give some explanation, which will be reported by the note keeper in Table B (Google docs word file). **Table B** contains vertically and horizontally the stakeholders and in the matrix, they can add details about the characteristics of the links/relationships.

Presentation of task 3 – participants in group 2 are asked to show their Miro frame and briefly explain their main outcomes. Group 1 is asked to check during this presentation their main differences/other outcomes and in their presentation, they must focus on the additional and/or other links/relations. These can be briefly discussed plenary.

- **Break-**

During the break, the scientific expert and facilitator add the arrows of group 1 to the map of group 2 and re-organise the map where necessary for clarity (maybe 20 minutes is needed).

3.6 Assessing stakeholders' influence on risk analysis process- power mapping

The **goals** are to obtain consensus on the network (previous task) and to assess how much influence each stakeholder has on the risk analysis process and the overall goal (deciding on the actual risk of the food issue under study, how to manage and communicate it), this is the so-called power mapping.

After the break, the facilitator shows the synthesised map and asks if participants agree with the linkages between stakeholders (as shown in the social network) and if any changes should be made. Take time for reaching a consensus.

Then, the facilitator introduces the next task and the use of the Mentimeter tool

Task 4 - Each participant indicates the power (degree of influence) of each stakeholder in the Net Map. The scores range from no, small, moderate, to high influence) in Mentimeter.

The facilitator summarises briefly the main observations – who are the actors with the most and the least power based on the rating of all participants in the Mentimeter results?

In the meantime, the research assistant must adjust the size of the sticky notes representing a stakeholder. There are three sizes, namely small [S], medium [M] and large [L] for sticky notes. We advise you to test this in advance and decide when a small, medium, or large sticky note is assigned.

Depending on how much time is needed, the facilitator can conduct an energizer or give another short break.

3.7 Identifying and prioritising constraints in the SPS collaboration system

The **goal** is to identify and prioritise constraints in the current social network i.e. the SPS collaboration system in risk analysis.

The facilitator introduces the task and explains the different types/categories of constraints i.e. 1) in capabilities of stakeholders (i.e. knowledge, experience, mandate); 2) resources (human, financial); 3) relations between stakeholders (i.e. communication-related); others (participants can typify it themselves). The facilitator asks again to assign a rapporteur and the groups have the same note keeper.

Miro frames 11 (group 1 & 2) each group has its frame which lists three columns representing the three categories (and a section 'other'). There are sticky notes which participants can use to describe the identified constraints and put them in the right column

Task 5- The participants work in the same two groups (in break out rooms) and are asked to **identify** (possible or known) constraints in capabilities, resources, and relationships between

stakeholders that may compromise the risk analysis process. They must put their remarks on differently coloured sticky notes; each represents another category of constraint. The participants all work on the same Miro board but in the breakout rooms. The groups need to assign a rapporteur. The note keeper reports more detailed comments (than written on the sticky notes) in **Table C**.

After presenting all participants are asked to distribute three sticky dots (score 1, 2 and 3- less urgent, moderate, highly urgent) to three constraints to **prioritise the constraints**. The constraints with most points are considered as most urgent.

Presentation of task 5- Each group presents the main findings and the other participants can reflect/react.

The facilitator leads the discussion and monitors the time. Then, the facilitator explains the second part of task 5- prioritising.

The research assistant sums the scores and confirms for which constraints in capability, resources, and relationship the scored were highest (so most urgent). The facilitator summarises the findings and asks participants to reflect on it

3.8 Finalising the workshop

The facilitator makes a short round to ask participants' experience with the NetMap and the insights gained.

FoodSafety4EU

MULTI-STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM
FOR FOOD SAFETY IN EUROPE

<https://foodsafetyplatform.eu>